

Exploration and Mitigation of the Impact of Lighting Conditions on Multi-spectral Image Classification

Savvas Sifnaios¹, Ioannis Zorzos¹, George Arvanitakis¹, Fotios K. Konstantinidis¹,
Georgios Tsimiklis¹, and Angelos Amditis¹

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Abstract—Imaging spectroscopy is a potent and versatile technique, offering valuable spatial and spectral data across a diverse range of applications such as agriculture, environmental monitoring, material characterization and remote sensing. Nevertheless, due to its passive nature, multi-spectral and hyperspectral sensors heavily rely on appropriate illumination sources, especially in scenarios where natural sunlight might be insufficient or unavailable. To comprehend the challenges associated with illumination source selection, an extended experimental effort has been launched to investigate the effects of different lighting conditions on multi-spectral image analysis. A dataset of images captured from both the visible (16 bands) and Near-Infrared (25 bands) spectral regions under Full-Spectrum halogen and visible-spectrum LED illumination sources, was generated. Within this dataset, four distinct types of plastic waste, namely High Density PolyEthylene (HDPE), Low Density PolyEthylene (LDPE), PolyEthylene Terephthalate (PET), as well as PolyPropylene (PP), are incorporated. A set of machine learning models aim to distinguish the different kind of plastics. The models' accuracy, was employed as metric to quantify the impact different lighting conditions have on multi-spectral image classification. This work underlines the necessity of appropriate illumination sources on such imaging applications, while providing crucial insights to mitigate the effects of light conditions on the classification performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Both hyperspectral and multi-spectral imaging are emerging methodologies that acquire and analyse both spatial and spectral data pertaining to an object or scene. In contrast to conventional visual sensors, i.e. RGB cameras, which perceive visible light through three distinct bands (red, green, and blue), multi-spectral imaging involves the division of the electromagnetic spectrum into numerous bands that span from ultraviolet to long infrared wavelengths [1]. Multi-spectral imaging has demonstrated its applicability across various industries and domains, including remote sensing, agriculture, recycling, mineralogy, and medicine [2], [3].

Recently, there has been an increasing utilisation of hyperspectral and multi-spectral technology in material waste sorting machines within the domains of plastic, construction and demolition, wood, and glass feedstocks. The fundamental component of these systems is the cameras, which serve

as the visual sensors of the machines [4]. In addition to the careful selection of sensors within appropriate spectral ranges for successful sorting, it is important to consider the impact of lighting conditions on image quality [5], [6]. Since sorting applications are typically conducted in enclosed spaces, where natural sunlight is completely absent, the choice of the illumination source to substitute the full range spectrum emitted by the sun has a notable impact on the effectiveness of the spectral-driven decision-making process.

A wide range of technologies is employed for the illumination of the samples in multi-spectral imaging applications to highlight the spectral content and enhance the analysis of such data. The halogen lamp is amongst the most commonly used lighting source, offering broad spectral range and high color temperature. Their ability to produce continuous, well-balanced light makes them particularly suitable for applications such as remote sensing, agriculture, and material identification, where capturing detailed spectral information across a wide range of wavelengths is crucial [7], [8]. In addition to halogen lamps, such applications have explored several other illumination sources to cater to different requirements and scenarios. One notable example is light-emitting diodes (LEDs). LEDs offer advantages such as compact size, low power consumption, and flexibility in spectral output [9]. They can be easily tuned to emit light at specific wavelengths, making them ideal for targeted spectral analysis and selective illumination [10].

To investigate the effects of various illumination sources in multi-spectral image analysis, a machine learning methodology has been designed, implemented and evaluated for the classification of common plastic waste. To this end, a set of plastic waste samples has been selected and photographed under two different lighting conditions, i.e. under a full-spectrum halogen light bar emitting light in the range of 400-2400nm and under a LED lamp which covers only the visible region of the electromagnetic spectrum (400-800nm). A pre-processing pipeline, including spectral calibration, smoothing and normalization steps, has been deployed and applied to the images to create the input for the machine learning classification algorithms. The accuracy of the classifiers has been used to quantify the effects of different lighting conditions in the hyperspectral imaging analysis. Finally, mitigation measures for the shortcomings of the illumination sources are proposed to improve the models' performance.

The contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- The introduction of comprehensive analysis on the effects of different lighting conditions in industrial, clas-

¹Savvas Sifnaios, Ioannis Zorzos, George Arvanitakis, Georgios Tsimiklis, Angelos Amditis and are with the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, National Technical University of Athens, 9 Iroon. Polytechniou Str., Zografou Athens GR-157 73, Greece{savvas.sifnaios, ioannis.zorzos, giorgos.arvanitakis, fotios.konstantinidis, georgios.tsimiklis, and angelos.amditis}@iccs.gr

sification applications that incorporate multi-spectral imaging sensors.

- The implementation of a robust, computer vision methodology for spectral features extraction, based on image segmentation and pixel selection.
- The development of mitigation measures for each illumination source's limitations.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Chapter II describes the related work, while Chapter III provides a description of the system architecture on a high-level and the illumination sources used. The datasets created for the needs of this work are presented in Chapter IV, as well as the machine learning classifiers. Moreover, this section introduces the preprocessing pipeline and the training of the model, along with the respective classification results. In addition, mitigation approaches for the limitations of the illumination sources are discussed. In Chapter V the conclusions of this study and future extensions are presented.

II. RELATED WORK

Numerous investigations have delved into the influence of diverse lighting arrangements and settings on imaging spectroscopy and the effect on the precision of classification. While there is limited research specifically focused on the effects of different lighting setups on classification accuracy, some studies have provided insights into this topic. A recent study investigated the effect of shadows on the classification accuracy of hyperspectral images and proposed a physics-based deep learning approach to address this issue. The proposed method was shown to be effective in improving the illumination invariance of the features and could be used to improve the performance of high-level perception algorithms that operate on images acquired outdoors [11]. In a similar vein, Nansen et al. [12] centered their research on the categorization of agricultural products using hyperspectral imaging. Their findings indicated that the selection of lighting had a substantial impact on the accuracy of classification, with the most favorable outcomes achieved under natural light.

Moreover, a study used both ground-based and drone-based hyperspectral imagers to image plants and found that classification accuracies ranged from 77% to 99% for spectra acquired on their ground-based imaging platform and from 25% to 79% on their drone-based platform, depending on the plants imaged and lighting conditions. While this study did not directly measure the effects of different lighting setups on classification accuracy, it provides some information on the lighting conditions used in their experiments and the resulting classification accuracies [13]. In a distinct field, tissue classification using hyperspectral imaging is also highly dependent by the illumination settings. It is suggested that the precision of tissue categorization could be enhanced by meticulously choosing the lighting setup [14]. Collectively, these studies underscore the significance of the lighting setup in hyperspectral imaging and its impact on classification accuracy across a variety of domains.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

In this chapter, a detailed description of Cyber-Physical Sorting System (CPSS) and the multi-spectral camera modules utilized for the image acquisition is provided. Moreover, the technical details of the two different light sources used for the illumination of the plastic waste samples are presented.

A. Cyber-Physical Sorting System

In this study, the previously proposed Cyber-Physical Sorting system [15] was utilized to acquire multi-spectral images under diverse lighting conditions. By leveraging the system's versatility, various illumination sources were examined and data for the comprehensive analysis were captured.

Fig. 1: The experimental setup used for the dataset creation: In this figure the conveyor belt of Cyber-Physical Sorting System is depicted (left side), as well as the multi-spectral visual sensors used in this work (right side).

As shown in Fig. 1, the system consists of conveyor belt, that allows horizontal translation of the objects at adjustable speed and a set of multi-spectral cameras ample of capturing both spatial and spectral information of the objects moving along the conveyor's belt. Both camera heads are equipped with a CMOS-based filter structure covering the spectral region between 470nm and 975nm. To this end, the first multi-spectral module (VIS) incorporates a *CMV2K-SSM4x4* snapshot-mosaic sensor capturing images in the visible range of 470-620nm with 16 distinct bands, while the latter one (NIR) is equipped with the *CMV2K-SSM5x5* snapshot-mosaic sensor, allowing the acquisition of images with 25 bands in the range 600-975nm.

B. Illumination sources

In the scope of this study, two different types of illumination sources were selected to examine how various lighting conditions affect the quality of multi-spectral data, hence the classification results of machine and deep learning algorithms. To this end, a **Full-Spectrum halogen bar light** and a **visible-spectrum Light Emitting Diode (LED)** were utilized to illuminate the plastic waste samples.

The Full-Spectrum bar light utilized is a custom-made LDL-222X42CIR manufactured by CCS Inc. and consists of

4 distinct halogen lamps that emit light in different regions of the spectrum, with a nominal wattage of 87W, covering, this way, the spectral range from 400nm to 2400nm. This illumination source, is equipped with a diffusion layer, that spreads the emitted light evenly in multiple directions, thus resulting in more uniform illumination of the scene and the objects within. On the other hand, the LED light source consists of one conventional lamp with nominal maximum wattage of 300W, that emits warm white light in a non-diffused manner in the visible and very Near-Infrared spectral region, i.e. 400-800nm.

The illumination sources were positioned on the CPSS, as depicted in Fig. 1. In detail, it was mounted at a vertical distance of **0.5m** from the conveyor's belt plane, at an angle of **45 degrees** and at a horizontal distance of **0.3m** from the center of multi-spectral cameras' lenses. Fig. 2 depicts the normalized intensity, with respect to the maximum value, of the spectral responses of each illumination source.

Fig. 2: Spectral response of the illumination sources utilized: On the left side the spectral response of the full-spectrum halogen bar light source is presented, while the respective response of the LED source is presented on the right side.

Upon examination, it becomes apparent that the Full-Spectrum source has smoother spectral response curve with a relative intensity $>65\%$ from 600nm to 1600nm, and a peak at 1000nm. For greater wavelengths, the source's illumination efficiency reduces rapidly, which however has no impact to this work since the multi-spectral cameras sample spectral information up to 975nm. On the contrary, in the respective curve of the LED source, multiple peaks and minima are identified, with the most prominent being at 450nm (blue light region) and 570nm (green light region). Moreover, in the LED light source case the relative illumination intensity is evidently lower than the Full-Spectrum's one in the respective wavelengths. Founded on the spectral response differences between the two types of illumination, a comprehensive analysis to investigate the effects of lighting conditions in multi-spectral imaging is conducted.

C. System Calibration

The precise calibration of the imaging system is an essential prerequisite for obtaining high-quality data, ensuring the accuracy and reliability of subsequent analyses. Prior to the spectral calibration of the sensors, the respective illumination sources and imaging modules were activated, and a 10-minute equilibration period was instituted to facilitate the

attainment of their steady-state temperature conditions. In this manner, the thermal noise produced is incorporated in the multi-spectral images and compensated through the calibration of the cameras. The sensors calibration involves the acquisition of images of a Spectralon Diffuse Target under each lighting condition. The target is ample of reflecting uniformly light across the range [250nm - 2500nm]. By analyzing the captured data from the target, each camera's spectral calibration curve, which relates the camera's recorded intensities to the true spectral values at each wavelength, is computed. The resulting curve can then be used to accurately convert raw camera data into precise spectral information, enabling the camera to capture and provide high-quality data.

IV. MULTISPECTRAL IMAGE ANALYSIS

To evaluate the effects lighting conditions have on multi-spectral image analysis, a set of one-dimensional-input machine algorithms were selected to classify plastic waste samples. In order to train the aforementioned algorithms, common plastic waste samples were photographed under the two examined lighting conditions, thus creating two distinct sets of multi-spectral images. A modular preprocessing pipeline was, also, designed and developed intending to generate the input feature vectors. The machine learning models were trained on those feature vectors and the classification performance was treated as a measure of influence on the images' quality. Finally, mitigation approaches are proposed for overcoming each illumination source's shortcomings.

A. Datasets

For the needs of this work, two different datasets of multi-spectral (VIS and NIR) images from commercially available plastic materials were created. Both datasets contain images of the same plastic samples and differentiate only on the lighting source used to illuminate the scene. The plastic waste samples were positioned underneath the camera heads, aiming for a centered alignment. The multi-spectral images were then captured with an integration time of **2ms** to ensure optimal exposure and clarity, in both cases. The categories of plastic waste comprising the datasets are: High Density PolyEthylene (HDPE), Low Density PolyEthylene (LDPE), PolyEthylene Terephthalate (PET) and PolyPropylene (PP).

Fig. 3: Near-infrared false colour representation of the 4 plastic waste classes: In the first row the NIR images using the visible LED source are depicted, while in the latter one depicts the same objects under the Full-Spectrum lighting.

In Fig.3 the false colour representation of the Near-Infrared images of the same objects is presented. In both cases, the representation was generated by selecting the same three spectral bands (776nm, 865nm and 971nm). It is apparent, however, that the illumination source utilized during image capture imparts distinct color variations to the images. In the LED lighting scenario, the images exhibit a noticeable yellow hue, whereas in the Full-Spectrum lighting scenario, they display a green hue. This discrepancy indicates that the band assigned to represent the green color (865nm) demonstrates higher intensity values under Full-Spectrum lighting, suggesting a direct influence of the illumination source on the pixel intensity values on the images. Moreover, in the case of the HDPE sample, when illuminated by the diffused Full-Spectrum light, evidently, fewer shadows are present compared to the image captured when the object was illuminated by the non-diffused LED light.

In total, 83 images were collected per sensor for each lighting condition, and class distributions in the resulting datasets are shown in Table I.

TABLE I: Number of samples per class in the two datasets.

Category	HDPE	LDPE	PET	PP
Number	21	17	20	25

B. Preprocessing Pipeline

A crucial step in multi-spectral image analysis is the preprocessing of the acquired data, as it enhances their overall quality by transforming and normalizing raw data. Moreover, a well-designed preprocessing pipeline increases the dataset’s signal-to-noise ratio by handling missing values or outliers and removing various types of noise, thus aiding in the models’ better classification performance.

To this end, a preprocessing pipeline was implemented ample of adjusting the spectral transformation, smoothing, normalization and noise reduction algorithms applied to the input data, depending on the application’s requirements. In detail, the pipeline consists of an algorithm responsible for identifying and replacing corrupted pixels through median filtering, a reverse decoupling methodology that converts the raw data into the, so-called, 3D hypercubes of shape 512×270 where each channel contains the spectral information of a specific band. Moreover, the *Savitsky-Golay filter* (SG) [16], for spectral smoothing and differentiation, is employed, as well as *Standard Normal Variate* regularization for dealing with light scattering effects. Finally, the proposed pipeline is capable of converting the raw values to *relative reflectance*, with respect to the illumination source, and normalizing the pixel values to the range of $[0,1]$.

Except for the spectral pretreatment of the images in the two sets, a methodology for pixel selection was necessary for the extraction of 1D feature to feed the models. As the datasets consist of multi-spectral images, i.e. 3D hypercubes, binary masks were manually generated for the images in each dataset and used as guidelines for the pixel selection process. By leveraging these masks, N central pixels and

$m \times m$ regions around them are extracted from the original image. The mean value, along the first two dimension of the aforementioned regions is calculated, thus creating the 1D input vectors, whose size is equal to the number of the spectral bands contained in the image from which they were extracted. This process is depicted on a high-level in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: A High-level flowchart of the 1D feature vectors extraction from the 3D Hypercube.

C. Models & Training

In the scope of this study, three distinct machine learning algorithms were implemented in order to examine how various lighting conditions affect their classification performance of multi-spectral data. In detail, a *Feed Forward Neural Network* architecture, consisting of 2 fully connected hidden layers and a 4-neuron output layer responsible for the class probability estimation, as well as a *1D Convolutional Neural Network* with one convolutional layer, one fully-connected hidden layer and a 4-neuron output layer were developed. The last algorithm implemented, is a *XGBoost* model with its maximum depth limited to 20 levels, and the number of leaves being set to 40.

A common preprocessing pipeline was employed with the exact same algorithms and parameters for the training process of all the aforementioned models. Particularly, the images in both datasets were scanned for corrupted pixels, converted into 3D hypercubes, had their spectra smoothed with SG filter of windows length $7p$ and polynomial order 2, and their values were normalized between the range $[0,1]$. Subsequently, the 1D feature vectors were extracted, by setting $N = 5000$ and $m = 4$ as explained in Chapter IV-B. Those feature vectors were, then, split into train, validation and test set following a 80%-10%-10% scheme.

The *Cross Entropy Loss* was selected as a cost function for the optimization problem and the *Adaptive Stochastic Gradient Descent* algorithm [17] was utilized for its minimization. The optimal models’ parameters were calculated after 20 epochs of training for the *Feed Forward Neural Network* and after 30 epochs for the *1D Convolutional Neural Network*.

D. Results

In this section, the classification performance of each model, under the two distinct lighting conditions, is discussed. Fig. 5 shows the progression of the loss function of the deep learning classifiers and their accuracy score on the validation set. Upon examining those curves, the models’

Fig. 5: Evolution of Cross Entropy loss during training and of Overall Accuracy during validation for both deep learning classifiers.

capacity to fit the training dataset without losing their ability to generalize their inference to unseen data is verified, since the training losses are decreasing monotonically and the validation accuracy scores are increasing as epochs pass.

As in the training phase, described in Section IV-C, the same test subset of 1D feature vectors was utilized for the evaluation of the models. The accuracy scores of the models in the test set are summarized in Table II. It is easily deduced that the *Feed Forward Neural Network* with the Full-Spectrum illumination source achieves the best performance, compared to the other algorithms, with an overall accuracy of **90%**. However, the most valuable information extracted from this table is the fact that when the samples are illuminated with the Full-Spectrum source, all the models, regardless of the multi-spectral sensors, have higher accuracy scores. In detail, substituting the LED light source with the Full-Spectrum one entails a **10%** and **5.5%** mean improvement in the performance of the *Feed Forward Neural Network* and *1D Convolutional Neural Network* respectively. The *XGBoost* algorithm, on the other hand, shows some kind of invariance in terms of the illumination source, since the accuracy for the VIS sensor is identical in both lighting conditions and slightly improves (**1%**) in the NIR sensor case. This fact is indicative of the model’s ability to extract more robust representations of the information encoded in samples with few features, like in this study, achieving a **89%** accuracy when the Full-Spectrum lighting is utilized.

TABLE II: Classification performance of models under different lighting conditions.

Model / Illumination source	LED		Full-Spectrum	
	VIS	NIR	VIS	NIR
Feed Forward NeuralNetwork	74.0%	81.0%	85.0%	90.0%
1D Convolutional Neural Network	76.0%	80.0%	80.0%	87.0%
XGBoost	83.0%	88.0%	83.0%	89.0%

In order to address the shortcomings of the visible LED illumination source, a set of mitigation approaches is proposed and validated by the best combination of model and type of sensor, i.e. with the *Feed Forward Neural Network* processing the NIR images.

Reflectance Transformation: The first approach is the conversion of the raw pixel values to relative reflectance values, with respect to the lighting source. In this manner,

variations in lighting conditions and sensor responses are compensated, thus enhancing a sample’s spectral features. The reflectance transformation is described by:

$$R = \frac{I - D^O}{W - D^{Ref}} \frac{t_{Ref}}{t_O}, \quad (1)$$

where R is the reflectance image, I is the original image captured by each camera sensor, D^{Ref} is the black reference image captured with integration time t_{Ref} equal to the exposure time used for the capturing of the white reference image W , D^O is another black reference image captured, however, with integration time t_O equal to the exposure time used for capturing the object’s image.

By integrating this methodology in the preprocessing pipeline, a *Feed Forward Neural Network* was trained to classify NIR images captured under the two distinct lighting conditions. The classifiers, achieved **95.6%** and **98.3%** accuracy scores under the LED and Full-Spectrum sources respectively, in the test set, which translates to 15.4% increase in performance for the LED illumination case and 8.3% increase for the latter case. This vast performance improvement, especially in the LED illumination source case, proves the effectiveness of the proposed method, in removing effects related to the lighting conditions and highlighting the spectral correlations among the feature vectors. Fig. 6 depicts the confusion matrices of the two models’ inference on the test set, in which it is evident that the majority of the samples are correctly assigned to their respective class.

Spectral Derivatives: The second mitigation measure for increasing the models’ performance is related to the aforementioned Savitsky-Golay (SG) filter. Instead of using the spectral signal for the classification of the NIR images, their 1st derivative is calculated and fed to the *Feed Forward Neural Network*. In this manner, the preprocessing pipeline was updated, again, to additionally calculate the derivative of the spectra through the application of the SG filter, and the same training scheme was followed, as in the reflectance case. The reported accuracy score was **97.1%** when the LED light source was employed and **99.3%** in the latter case. This improvement indicates the presence of constant noise in the spectra, that is eliminated through their differentiation.

In conclusion, the Full-Spectrum source emerged as the most appropriate illumination source, since when utilized

Fig. 6: Confusion Matrices of the NIR classifiers, presenting each class's percentage of correctly classified instances.

the overall models' performance was superior to the one achieved with the LED source. The maximum accuracy score of **99.3%** was achieved during the classification of NIR images, illuminated by the aforementioned source, with the *Feed Forward Neural Network*.

V. CONCLUSION & FUTURE DIRECTION

The comprehensive analysis conducted in this work underlines the necessity of careful consideration of lighting conditions, that provide adequate illumination across all examined wavelengths, for obtaining high-quality multi-spectral images. By investigating the classification performance of three machine learning algorithms, the Full-Spectrum source proved to be the most suitable illumination choice, while the LED one struggled to highlight the important spectral features for plastic waste separation. To address the identified shortcomings of the LED source, mitigation measures were proposed that increased the accuracy under both illumination conditions, resulting in **99.3%** classification accuracy of the NIR images captured under the Full-Spectrum source.

In future research, the utilization of hyperspectral cameras that sample a wavelength range up to 2500nm is intended. By exploiting the additional spectral information, more accurate results on the lighting influence will be obtained. Moreover, leveraging the acquired intelligence from this work and the higher spectral resolution of the hyperspectral cameras will

allow for further analysis on the spectral band selection and model optimization.

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